

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PROJECT DEVELOPMENT PROCESS IN PROJECT-TELLING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract

The present work is devoted to the project development process in educational organization in the Project-telling methodology for ensure project and organization's reputation stability with help of frameworks: strategic, systematic, scenario and branding planning.

Keywords: Project-telling, project, marketing of educational organizations, positioning of universities, positioning of colleges, expertise of educational organizations, recognition of educational organizations, market for educational services.

The purpose of the article is considered the technic to develop an effective, positioning project and to ensure project sustainability.

The project development stage defines, what the organization says about itself through the project. The work on designing a project can be represented in the form of three successive stages:

1. Definition of the project framework,
2. Formation of the project content,
3. Testing and assessment of readiness for project implementation.

The proposed project development methodology in the logic of Project-telling¹ is based on three principles - SSB: strategic analysis, system analysis (searching for the expertise of an educational organization), branding.

Storytelling Project, as a method of deep positioning in constantly changing conditions, is a three-dimensional, multifaceted entity and is designed in a three-dimensional coordinate system in which each of the principles forms axial directions.

To develop project content, it is extremely important to define the framework (frame) of the project, the work area, and the project desktop. The brain's abilities are enhanced when there are clear boundaries. The best way to become a creative person is not to stimulate limitless flights of thought, but rather to determine exactly where the limits are. The more specific you are, the easier it is to think creatively.

How to implement the framework?

Strategic analysis during project development:

If the organization plans to participate in this type of project for the first time:

- Analysis of the investment attractiveness of the direction,
- Analysis of the positions and competitive advantages of organizations existing in this project (SWOT analysis),
- Possible share in the project,
- Long-term forecast of project development,
- Regional and international cooperation within the project and prospects for the export of services.

If the organization is already involved in this type of project:

- Analysis of the organization's position in the project over time,
- Analysis of changes in the activities of competitors in the project,
- Changing the behavior of consumers, participants, target groups,
- Changing channels of information about the project,
- New factors influencing the project (PEST-analysis),
- Study of project risks.

Strategic analysis contains in-depth, structured information based on detailed analysis of statistical and analytical data.

Strategic analysis is performed on the basis of primary and secondary information:

- Data from the National Statistics Service,
- Data from relevant ministries,
- Data from relevant public organizations,
- Data of project operators,
- Data from specialized information resources and media,
- Results of sociological and marketing research (collected through questionnaires, focus groups, interviews),
- Internet audience analysis data.

As a rule, the strategic analysis is carried out on the basis of data for the last 3-5 years with a forecast of market development for 2-3 years (baseline, optimistic and pessimistic scenario).

In the context of global economic challenges, the issue of strategy remains relevant, but acquires additional content. Increasingly, experts are talking about a flexible strategy, about strategy in conditions of turbulence, about proactive activities ahead of the curve.

When faced with dilemmas caused by a crisis, managers may become fixated on one scenario and continue to follow their usual problem-solving methods. In turbulent environments, this can make the organization less flexible.

In such conditions, strategy is especially important, but the approach to it must change.

¹ Anisimova I.A. Project-telling: positioning by projects / Anisimova I.A. - Moscow: Litres, 2024. - 177 p. - ISBN - 978-5-532-90770-6.

What's why is necessary the transition to strategic thinking.

The planning horizon has shortened for various reasons, and the organization requires a transition from strategy to the formation of strategic thinking among key employees in the team.

Strategy is a plan and an answer to the question "why". In this logic, both the plan and the answer to the question "why" can change regularly, and everyone chooses the level of detail for themselves. If you regularly monitor these components, you can more effectively anticipate and navigate changes, even crisis ones.

Strategy Objectives

Over the past three years, it has become clear that the purpose of strategy has changed from being a guide document to a dynamic tool. This approach does not cancel key strategic documents, but translates them into a more lively and flexible format, the goals and priorities of which are especially important in a crisis, where the focus is on team synchronization.

In this regard, we more often see a revision of strategic goals. This, for example, happened with Sberbank, which until 2020 moved on 3-4 year horizons. However, in 2020, a new strategy was adopted, which revised the goals and plans and launched the process of ecosystem reform in late 2021-early 2022.

Strategy Synchronization

Companies are increasingly approaching strategy in an agile manner and viewing it as an ongoing function responsible for monitoring gaps between the internal state and the external context of the company. If these gaps become critical, companies update their strategy.

In such circumstances, it is important to understand and agree on what actions will be taken and what actions will not be taken. At the same time, managers and the team regularly check their actions and understanding of goals and objectives, which is the synchronization of strategy and strategic dialogue.

Scenario planning

To avoid the constant need to adapt, some companies formulate a portfolio of actions outright, including bets in case the context changes. An approach that allows this to be done and becomes especially popular in times of permanent crises is scenario planning. It is used to anticipate risks and opportunities and organize the strategic thinking of business leaders.

Scenario planning is one way to formulate hypotheses at a strategic level, in the context of existing drivers and uncertainty. This approach helps prepare the company for new challenges, adapt to constantly changing conditions and generally increase business sustainability.

Strategic approach

In the current reality, the strategic approach consists of three key steps:

- ✓ Agree where the company is heading, what priorities and goals it faces,
- ✓ Formalize these agreements in the company language (documents, orders, presentations, etc.),
- ✓ Implement these goals into the life of the company through related processes, for example, through a clear HR cycle.

Scenario planning is structured as follows:

- ✓ Time frames, industrial and geographical limitations are indicated - for what period and for what purpose the scenarios are being developed.
- ✓ Key uncertainties are identified - what fixes the company's management the most and is the most vulnerable point that can adapt last.
- ✓ Images of the future and 4 options for their development are created, based on two key uncertainties.
- ✓ Possible consequences are identified, focusing on those risks and opportunities that could have the greatest impact on the business.

Today Scenario planning is one of the most effective approaches to strategic management. Its effectiveness is expressed in the proactive analysis of the risks of different scenarios and the identification of signals at which different action protocols should be triggered. Now such approaches are used in various industries: from manufacturing and development to HoReCa and financial services.

An effective algorithm for developing scenarios:

- 1) Identify several scenarios. When conducting an analysis, it is important to develop options. Remember not to have too many so that you can get quality focus on each one.
- 2) Get a different estimate. Discuss the scenarios with a variety of people both inside and outside your company, such as business consultants.
- 3) Synchronize understanding of strategy across the company. Move from abstract strategy to specific plans and projects for the coming year and find the leaders of these projects.
- 4) Plan regularly. Conduct strategy sessions to always remain flexible and adapt to external changes. Remember that strategic thinking is not about a document for 3-5 years, but about an adaptive approach and regular practice.

System analysis during project development:

Design begins with understanding the value of the organization, for which the target audience is ready to come and, if necessary, pay. What in-demand product (determined based on the results of strategic analysis) does the organization offer to the market? Project-telling tells the public exactly about the value of the organization.

In order to answer the question about the value of an organization, it is necessary to carry out a systems analysis. This approach came to management from the technical sciences as an applied direction of systems theory, which is used in solving complex poorly formalized problems. In particular, systems analysis experts D. Cleland and W. King developed the application of systems concepts to management functions associated with strategic planning and goal setting.

System analysis became widespread after the publication of S. Optner's book "System Analysis for Solving Business and Industrial Problems". The value of the systems approach is that consideration of the categories of system analysis creates the basis for a logical and consistent approach to the problem of decision making.

System analysis allows, at the project design stage, to eliminate the randomness of the first results and comply with the principle of validity.

The key task of system analysis in project development is to search for the organization's expertise, especially in the areas of market growth identified in the strategic analysis.

For this purpose, an approach is used - the so-called Helicopter view, a panoramic view of the organization from above as an integral object in a complex of elements and connections that form an organic whole in interaction, in which a change in one of the elements leads to a change in other elements.

For example, the task is to develop a project to receive a grant for a team developing a technological product (nominations can be in different areas of modern science and technology). In order to carry out a system analysis, it is necessary to identify the object, its components and factors influencing efficiency.

So, the object is to determine an effective team for developing a technological product at a university.

The elements will be the presence of patents, developments, the presence of a sufficient number of scientific employees (age, academic degree, academic title, income), the presence of a material and technical base, the availability of premises, expert recognition of the direction (expressed in the number of articles in the direction for a certain period of time, prizes, awards at various levels), etc. It is important to display the relationship of the elements, as well as the factors influencing the elements and the direction of the dynamics of these elements over the past 3 years, 10 years, 20 years.

Elements and connections can be depicted graphically or using descriptions.

Another type of systems analysis is certain aspects of business analytics. For example, an educational organization can make a simple analysis based on financial and substantive performance results in various technological areas:

- Which areas have the most patents and certificates been received over the past 3 years, 10 years, 20 years?
- Which areas the largest number of grants have been won over the past 3 years, 10 years, 20 years?
- Which of the areas generates the maximum income from product development over the past 3 years, 10 years, 20 years?
- What areas is the maximum number of researchers?

In order to fit a nascent project into constantly changing conditions, the results of systemic and strategic analysis must be combined in the form of hypotheses - assumptions based on previously carried out analytics that the organization's expertise found can solve a market or social problem or fits into a trend of extreme demand.

Branding during the project development process²:

The storytelling project today is also based on branding. It is important not only to find expertise and fit it into changing market conditions, but also to find a concept for the sound and appearance of the proposed

solution, i.e. package it in a way that is cognitively understandable and aesthetically pleasing to the target audience.

The principle of brand formation is always the same, regardless of the market or sector. A brand is a set of images and associations of the audience about an organization and its brand, product, service.

How to develop a brand strategy?

The algorithm and sequence of steps are quite simple:

✓ We study the company/product and identify around what constants a brand can be formed (features of the product, its production, the company's values, features of its corporate culture, etc.).

✓ We study the external market and identify the stage of its development and competitive conditions (this greatly influences the type and type of brand strategy),

✓ We study the audience,

✓ We formulate a strategy, find an idea for a future brand, and build its platform.

Does it make sense to build a brand strategy taking into account the unpredictability of change?

A brand is a stable image in the minds of your audience. If the brand strategy is developed correctly, then "external conditions and conditions are dynamic and unpredictable. In such conditions, we build brands around constants that we can rely on (value-driven and purpose-driven approaches).

Your product can (or must) pivot in the face of uncertainty, but brands are much more resilient constructs.

How do you know if your brand strategy needs adjustment?

Каждый крупный бренд всегда измеряет свои атрибуты и их вес для аудитории. Иногда рынок формируется таким образом, что те территории для позиционирования, которые использовал бренд, становятся «общим местом» для всего рынка и каждого бренда на нем.

Do you need an additional strategy for insurance or do you still need to strictly stick to the main one?

If we are talking about brand strategy, then it is impossible to live with a "fallback option". Brands are built slowly, and changing this perception quickly as part of a "back-up strategy" will not work. That is why rebranding projects are much more complex and longer-term than introducing a new brand to the market. And no additional strategy for rent is possible.

So after designing the project's boundaries, we can move on to the content development stage. As with a house - when only after strong walls have been erected on a strong foundation, and a reliable roof has been built, is interior decoration, interior design, decoration, etc. possible.

² Anisimova, I.A. Brands of universities through the eyes of employers: the degree of trust in the quality of training of specialists / I.A. Anisimova // Vestnik of Nizhny Novgorod University. N.I. Lobachevsky: Social Sciences Series No. 1 (9). -

N. Novgorod: Publishing house of Nizhny Novgorod State University named after. N.I. Lobachevsky, 2008. – P.9-15. – ISSN 1811-5942.

References

1. Anisimova, I.A. Brands of universities through the eyes of employers: the degree of trust in the quality of training of specialists / I.A. Anisimova // Vestnik of Nizhny Novgorod University. N.I. Lobachevsky: Social Sciences Series No. 1 (9). - N. Novgorod: Publishing house of Nizhny Novgorod State University named after. N.I. Lobachevsky, 2008. – P.9-15. – ISSN 1811-5942.
2. Anisimova I.A. Project-telling: positioning by projects / Anisimova I.A. - Moscow: Litres, 2024. - 177 p. - ISBN - 978-5-532-90770-6.
3. Anisimova, I.A. Strategy and modern forms of development of professional competencies in an engineering university // Seventh international scientific and practical conference: Philosophy and culture of the information society: abstracts: at 2 o'clock. Part 2. – St. Petersburg: GUAP, 2019. – P.123-125. – ISBN 978-5-8088-1413-40 (Part 2).
4. Anisimova I.A., Krichevsky M.L., Martynova Yu.A. Development and implementation of artificial intelligence technologies in the educational process of the university: educational method. allowance. – St. Petersburg: GUAP, 2020. – 99 p.
5. Voronin, G.L., Anisimova, I.A. Sociological research program of the Career Center of Lobachevsky University in the design and implementation of activities for vocational guidance, employment and professional career implementation of students and graduates // Helping professions: scientific justification and innovative technologies / Under the general editorship of prof. Z.H. Saralieva. – N. Novgorod: Publishing house NISOC, 2016. – P. 315-318. - ISBN 978-5-93116-183-9.